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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON PHARMACY AND THERAPEUTIC
COMMITTEE****C. Swetha^{*1}, Dr. S. Rajesh Raja²,**¹Student Dr. K.V. Subbareddy Institute Of Pharmacy²Assistant Professor, Department Of Pharmacy Practice, Dr. K.V. Subbareddy Institute Of Pharmacy**Abstract:**

Pharmacy and Therapeutics Committee (PTC) is a group of multidisciplinary professionals within a hospital, responsible for managing an effective drug inventory, control and review of rational drug use and drug costs. Hospital PTCs are supervised by the Thai Ministry of Public Health. We would assess their effectiveness and, identify short-comings for which we offer solutions to improve their performance. The survey was focused on seven public hospitals in lower northern region of rural Thailand, forming an alliance and includes a university teaching unit. Three key PTC participants from each hospital were interviewed face-to-face using a semi-structured guide. Triangulation and content analysis were used for data analysis.

PTC members appreciated the importance of their roles, functions and particularly the importance of effective drug selection for the hospital formulary. However, PTC performance was compromised by; over-stretched committee staffs, inadequate budgetary considerations, personal and professional conflicts and prejudices, poor communication and performance monitoring, erratic national directives, and lack of standard criteria for drug selection. We suggest that the whole system be over-hauled via management of human resources, committee membership, and communication, creating tools for effective decision-making for rational drug selection, staff training and integrating PTC and rational drug use into medical curricular, and clear and consistent national regulation

Clearly, PTC effectiveness fell well short of the WHO recommendations. Although cost containment is a major issue, there are numerous cost-neutral changes which could improve PTC operation, effectiveness and which ultimately strengthens patient treatment.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The Pharmacy and Therapeutics Committee is an advisory group of the medical staff which serves as the organizational line of communication between the medical staff and pharmacy department. It is a policy recommending body to the medical staff and the administration of the hospital on matters related to drug use. This committee is composed of physicians, pharmacists and other health professional selected with the guidance of the medical staff.

It is a responsible for framing policies and procedures for selection, procurement, dispensing, labelling, availability, administration, and control of drugs throughout the hospital.

It encourages rational use of drugs in the hospital and monitors issues relating the drug.

2. OBJECTIVES OF PTC

1. Advisory
2. Education
3. Safe and Rational Use of Drugs

1. Advisory

- The committee recommends the adoption of policies or assists in the Formulation of broad professional policies regarding evaluation, selection, and therapeutic use of drugs in the hospital.
- The committee serves in an advisory capacity to medical staff and hospital administration in all matters pertaining to the use of drugs including the investigation of drugs.
- It makes recommendation concerning the drugs to be stocked in hospital patient care areas.
- The committee advises the pharmacy in implementation of effective drug distribution and control procedures.
- PTC is involved in all the matters related with the use of medicine in hospital.
- PTC assists in preparing the guidelines regarding evaluation, selection and therapeutic use of medicines in hospitals.
- Further the committee also provides the guidelines for hospital pharmacy related with the dispensing of drugs to patients.
- Policy includes various issues like who may prescribe or administer drug, direction during prescription and guidance, to assure safe and proper use of high risk, high volume, high cost or problem prone drugs.
- PTC also assist in the formulation of broad professional policies relating to drugs, regarding their selection, prescribing,

procurement, storage, distribution, administration, safety procedures, monitoring and use.

- Furthermore, PTC engaged in making rules and regulations for administration, monitoring and outcomes of drugs and diagnostic testing material.

2. Education

- The committee recommends or assists in the formulation of functions, designed to meet the needs of professional staff like the nurses, physicians, pharmacist, and other healthcare practitioners, for the complete current knowledge of the matter related to the drugs and their use.
- The committee evaluates the problems related to the distribution and administration of medications including medication incident.

3. Safe and rational use of drugs

This function is assigned to or taken up by the PTC and it should be continuous scheme of exerting vigilance. PTC overlooks safe, economic, and rational use of pharmaceutical across the healthcare facility.

3. ORGANIZATIONS AND OPERATIONS OF PTC

The PTC should be composed of at least three physicians, a pharmacist and representative of the nursing staff. Committee members are appointed by the governing unit or elected officials of the organized medical staff.

- The hospital administrator or his/her representative should be an ex-officio member of the committee. PTC monitors and reports all the ADR related with the drugs.
- A chairman from among the three physician's representatives should be appointed. A pharmacist usually designated as secretary.
- The committee should meet regularly at least six times per year, and when necessary.
- The committee should invite to its meeting person within or outside the hospital who can contribute specialized or unique knowledge, skills and judgment.
- An agenda and supplementary materials (including minutes of the previous meeting)
- Should be prepared by the secretary and submitted to the committee members in sufficient time before the meeting.
- Policies of Minutes of the committee meeting should be prepared by the secretary and maintained in the permanent records of the hospital.

- Recommendation of the committee shall be presented to the medical staff or its appropriate committee for adoption or recommendation.
- Liaison with other hospital committee concerned with drug use (e.g.; infection control, medical audit) shall be continued.
- Secretary should prepare the agenda and supplementary materials and submit it to committee members in sufficient time before each meeting for them to review the material properly.
- Secretary should prepare minutes of meetings and maintain in the permanent record of the organization.

Composition of PTC

- Physicians
- Pharmacist
- Nursing staff representative (medical staff)

4. FUNCTIONS OF PTC

- ❖ PTC advises the medical staff and hospital administrator in all matter related to use of drug (including investigational drug).
- ❖ Lay down of the written policies and procedures for the selection, procurement, storage and distribution and use of drugs including investigation of new drug.
- ❖ To develop and prepare hospital drug formulary.
- ❖ To develop norms and guideline for revision of formulary at regular interval and procedure for addition of new drug, deletion of old drugs, duplication of drug or its combination.
- ❖ To suggest measures to evaluate clinical data regarding new drug or agent.
- ❖ To establish or plants suitable educational program for hospital professional matter related to drug use.
- ❖ To review reported adverse drug reactions (ADR) to drug administered to the patients in the hospital.
- ❖ To evaluate problem related to the procurement, storage, distribution, and administration of drugs in hospital.
- ❖ To develop and establish generic and therapeutic substitution guidelines for the hospital.
- ❖ To advise pharmacy regarding drug distribution control procedures, developing drug information system maintenance of drugs standard and quality control, maintenance of records and disposal of expiry drugs.
- ❖ Prevent unnecessary loading of drug, prescribing and to promote rational therapeutic guidelines.

- ❖ Look after safe usage of drugs.
- ❖ To serve as an advisory administration in all matters related to the use of drugs.
- ❖ To develop & compile a formulary of drugs a prescription accepted for use in various hospitals, the selection of the items to be included in the formulary is based on their therapeutic use, safety, cost, etc.
- ❖ The committee should minimize duplication of the same basic drugs of their products.
- ❖ The committee recommends written Policies & procedures for selection, procurement, storage, distribution, and use of drugs.
- ❖ To Establish or plan suitable educational schemes for the hospital professional staff on the matter related to the Use of drugs.
- ❖ To study problems related to the distribution & administration of medications.
- ❖ To make recommendations concerning the drugs to be stocked in wards & emergency.
- ❖ To advise the pharmacy in the implementation of effective drug distribution E control procedures.

5. POLICIES OF PTC

The use drug in hospital is controlled by different policies which includes the Proposal of new drug for hospital formulary shall be submitted on formulary request form to pharmacy department.

Drug evaluated and approved by committee will be assigned to one of the following categories

- Formulary drug
- Drug approved on conditional trial period
- Specialized formulary drug
- Investigational drug
- Non formulary drug will not be stocked in pharmacy Rules and regulations which governs Pharma representative activity
- Pharmacy department authorized to dispense drug as per policies and procedure of PTC.
- Pre signing of blank prescription or drug order is prohibited.
- Drug recall.

In patients' prescription

- Routine drug order
- I.V orders
- Total Parental Nutritionist (TPN)
- Self-medication
- Medication broad to hospital by patients
- Discharge prescription

Outpatient prescription

- ❖ Hospitalized patient at discharge, clinic patients and employee's prescription only be written on hospital prescription form.
- ❖ Special requirement for control drug.

Therapeutic interchange

Therapeutic interchange provides pharmacists with the authorization to use a formulary therapeutic alternative in place of a non-formulary medication or a non-preferred formulary medication without having to contact the prescriber. Drugs appropriate for therapeutic interchange are drug products with different chemical structures that are expected to have similar therapeutic effects and safety profiles when administered to patients in therapeutically equivalent doses. A process is established for when the prescriber wishes to opt out of the interchange. Adequate educational initiatives should be undertaken to ensure that everyone affected (prescribers, patients, pharmacists, nurses, and other health care professionals) is notified of the therapeutic interchange. Guidelines on therapeutic interchange are available elsewhere.

Guided-use strategies

Medications may be added to the formulary with additional processes in place to guide the use of the medications to improve therapeutic outcomes, prevent adverse events, or reduce costs. Examples of strategies to help guide the use of medications in addition to therapeutic interchange may include the following.

Established-use criteria

Patients must meet the established criteria before the medication is dispensed. A process should be developed to cover situations in which the patient does not meet the established criteria, but the medication is nevertheless determined to be medically necessary. This strategy may also be useful when medications are in short supply.

Restricting drug use to a service

A specific service must approve the use of the drug before dispensing. This strategy can be used when inappropriate use or severe adverse effects may occur and it can also be employed for antimicrobial agents when inappropriate use or overuse can result in resistant organisms and pose a danger to the general patient population or the public.

Limiting use of the drug to specially trained individuals

This strategy may be appropriate when the drug is inherently dangerous and should only be used by

individuals with specific training (e.g., restricting use of chemotherapy agents to oncologists). Designating medications for use in specific areas. Such policies can be helpful when administration of a medication requires special equipment or staff with particular skills to use the medication safely (e.g., limiting neuromuscular blockers to operating rooms and critical care areas).

Policies of the PTC in including drugs into formulary

and prepares formulary based on following principles

- ✓ Effectiveness
- ✓ Safety
- ✓ Efficient
- ✓ Cost
- ✓ Patients centred.

The PTC should be using an evidence-based process in the evaluation of medications for formulary consideration.

The PTC should be provided with information that reflects a thorough, accurate, and unbiased review and analysis of the evidence available in the scientific literature.

The evaluation process should encourage objective consideration of clinical and care delivery information; facilitate communication, foster positive patient outcomes, and support safe and effective medication ordering, dispensing, administration, and monitoring

Evidence- based evaluation

Inclusion of a medication on a health system's formulary should reflect that an evidence-based evaluation of the relative merits and risks of the medication has been performed and that the institution's P&T committee, with input from appropriate experts, has determined that the medication is appropriate for routine use in the management of the patient population at that institution. To practice evidence-based medicine, practitioners must be proficient in retrieving, evaluating, and applying the biomedical literature to clinical practice.

Types of drug reviews

There are four major types of drug reviews; new drug monographs, re-evaluations of previous formulary decisions, therapeutic class reviews, and expedited reviews of newly approved medications. Because of the expertise and training of pharmacists should play a main part in the preparation and presentation of the drug review document to the PTC.

Elements of a drug-evaluation document

The drug evaluation document should present the proof in a manner that is through, is consistent from medication to medication, and provides all necessary facts and analysis to the PTC to allow for an informed formulary decision. Document structure may vary, depending on the needs of the specific health system and PTC, but the following elements are essential to all such documents:

- Brand and generic names
- FDA approval information, including date and FDA rating.
- Pharmacology and mechanism of action.
- FDA approved indications,
- Potential non-approved (off-label) uses,
- Dosage forms and storage,
- Recommended dosage regimens,
- Pharmacokinetic considerations,
- Use in special populations (e.g.; children, elderly, patients with renal or liver failure),
- Pregnancy category and use during breast-feeding,
- Comparisons of the drug s efficacy, safety, convenience, and costs with those of therapeutic alternatives (with evidence tables when feasible),
- Clinical trial analysis and critique,
- Medication safety assessment and recommendations (adverse drug reactions; drug-drug and drug - food interactions; specific therapy monitoring requirements; unusual administration, storage, or stability issues; and potential for medication errors such as look- alike or issues), and financial analysis, including pharmacoeconomic assessments.
- Formulary status recommendations may be included in the drug evaluation document. In some organizations, recommendations are not provided in the written document in order to promote an unbiased discussion by the P&T committee.
- Recommendations should consider the formulary status of a medication, as well as the need for restrictions, educational efforts, or policies and procedures to ensure safe and appropriate use within the health system.

Pharmacoeconomic assessments

It is done for new medications. When new medications being considered are found to be therapeutically equivalent to existing alternatives then the cost-minimization approach is appropriate. While cost-effectiveness analysis is another potentially useful analytic approach, it is not often used for formulary decision-making because of its

complexity and need for strong evidence or data. The academic value of this approach lies in its ability to show how little must be spent to achieve a particular margin of clinical advantage when comparing an alternative that is more expensive but safer or more efficacious.

Automatic stop order

The reminder which is given to review patient's medications and assess the need to continue therapy. Medications given to the patients must be reviewed by the prescribing physician due to various reasons. PTC formulates the rules and guidelines for the automatic stoppage of dangerous drugs administration to patients

- ❖ Dangerous drugs include Narcotic, Sedatives, Hypnotics, Antibiotics, Anticoagulants
- ❖ These dangerous drugs should be automatically discontinued after 48 hours after prescription
- ❖ The Narcotic, Sedatives and hypnotic drugs should be represcribed after 24 hours
- ❖ unless and until the drug should be prescribed in specified doses or may be reordered by the physician
- ❖ These drugs should be only continued or prescribed if,
- ❖ Physician writes the number of doses to be administered
- ❖ Physician specifies the time period for administration of drugs

ROLES OF PTC IN DIFFERENT DEPARTMENT

Role of Pharmacy and Therapeutic Committee in drug safety

- The hospital must employ a qualified and registered pharmacist with at least B. pharmacy degree as chief pharmacist and the rest with at least D. Pharm degree.
- The hospital should not permit non-pharmacy person to dispense and align the drug
- Hospital must provide adequate space and storage facility for the pharmacy
- The hospital should have policy regarding the use of research drugs in hospital and clinics
- The pharmacy should have adequate reference library text on pharmacology, toxicology, posology and general containing adequate information in pharmaceutical world.
- Drug safety includes responsibility from dispensing of drugs to drug-administration and then to observe possible adverse effects.

- PTC can play a major role in ensuring the drug-safety
- Following guidelines may sub serve the committee in ascertaining the adequate safety factor of the hospital pharmacy.
- A registered pharmacist - chief pharmacist-diploma holders
- Not permit non-pharmacist personal
- A sufficient number of qualified personal
- Adequate safe, work space, and storage facilities
- Have equipment necessary
- Automatic stop order-narcotics, hypnotics, anti-coagulants
- Firm policy-research drugs
- Drug formulary
- Outside its working hours
- Poisonous materials- non-poisonous materials
- External use drugs-internal use drug.
- Quality control measures, GMP during processing
- Teaching programme
- Periodical inspection
- Adequate reference library

Role of Pharmacy and Therapeutic Committee in drug utilization review

Drug utilization includes prescribing, dispensing, administrating, and ingesting of prescribing drugs to patient

This DUR helps in detection of

- Drug interaction
- Drug induced disease
- Drug potential and toxicity.

Role of Pharmacy and Therapeutic Committee in emergency list

Since time factor of very good urgency to most true emergency situations it is necessary of the pharmacy and therapeutic committee of a hospital to get prepared boxes containing drugs which should be available ready for the use of bedside.

1. Supply to maintain in emergency box.
2. Drugs for emergency box
3. Supplies for cabinet utility room.
4. Other emergency supplies.

Role of PTC in developing "emergency drug lists

- ❖ The Time Factor is necessary for the Pharmacy and Therapeutics Committee of a hospital to get prepared boxes containing emergency drugs which should be always available readily for use at the bed-side.
- ❖ List of such drugs and other supplies should compiled by Committee, and it should find their place in "Emergency Kits".

- ❖ After the emergency boxes have been placed in the wards, it is very essential and compulsory that a system is developed whereby they are checked daily either by the hospital pharmacists or by nursing supervisor responsible for the ward.

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